

Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan

The plan describes the planned measures to maximize the impact of the project, including the dissemination and exploitation measures that are planned, and the target group(s) addressed. Regarding communication measures and public engagement strategy, the aim is to inform and reach out to society and show the activities performed, and the use and the benefits the project will have for citizens.

Cover page

PROJECT	
Project number:	[101063854]
Project acronym:	[POLARPOL]
Project name:	[A look inside: domestic features and the implementation of human and environmental risk measures in European Antarctic Treaty Parties]
Date:	[25/07/2025]

OVERVIEW OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION PLAN

TABLE OF REFERENCE TO THE PROJECT'S PROPOSED COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

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A1	Share results through conference papers		
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COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES¹ TO GENERAL PUBLIC

CARRIED OUT ACTIVITIES JUN 2023 – JUL 2025

A5.1: Oral evidence: Environmental Audit Committee - The UK and the Antarctic environment (February 2024)

The United Kingdom House of Commons Environmental Audit Committee contacted me to provide oral evidence to representatives for their inquiry into the UK's relationship with the Antarctic and its environment. During my Secondment in the Hague, I took part of the session on the 5th February 2024, responding to several questions from MPs with regards the Antarctic governance, the main challenges for the region's environmental protection, and the role of Great Britain in it.

Means for communication used	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Audio-visual and written.	Antarctic policymakers.	Share information on the nuances and main trends of the Antarctic governance with representatives of the House of Commons (Great Britain).	https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/48242/documents/252483/default/

A6: Elaboration of PolarPol Visual Identity (July-September 2023)

From 11th July to 29th August 2023, I took the training course on *Visual Identity* at the University of the Arts London, producing PolarPol's Branding Guidelines. This training was complemented by the *Adobe Creative Cloud* course from the 4th to the 8th September 2023 at Chelsea College of Arts. The aim was to make a research project more relatable, helping the audience to learn about POLARPOL's work and to retain the project's shared information through targeted visuals.

¹ Ensure compliance with Article 17 of Grant Agreement

Means for communication used	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Designing the project's Branding Guidelines, which included: colour pallet; typography; logo; symbol; and secondary brand elements.	Antarctic stakeholders and the general public.	To produce higher engagement of stakeholders and broader audiences through a clear visual communication and branding of the project.	https://polarpol.awi.de

A7: PolarPol webpage and social media (October and November 2023)

Based on the creation of PolarPol branding guidelines, I have applied to establish a dedicated webpage to the project, hosted independently from AWI's website (but within its server). With the help of Lukas Minnermann, the webpage was launched in 2024 and gathers information of the different work packages and events that I participated.

After a meeting with AWI's social media expert (Marlena Witte), I also created a dedicated profile at Bluesky (<https://bsky.app/profile/polarpol.bsky.social>) for PolarPol. Likewise, project's updates were communicated through my profile in LinkedIn, which counted with an already established audience. Therefore, I could assure a larger reach of the project's posts and overall communication.

Means for communication used	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Posts on a dedicated webpage.	General public, polar researchers and stakeholders.	To share the project's actions and build a community of those interested to learn more about the intersection of science and polar politics.	https://polarpol.awi.de

A8: Podcast episode 'Glimpses of Antarctica' (May 2025)

You, Me & HIFMB is a podcast series from the Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB), led by Dr. Jan-Class Dajka, an interdisciplinary postdoc from HIFMB's Transfer office. On the 26th May 2025, I had the chance to seat with Jan and chat about diversity in the polar regions and how my own academic trajectory is defined by seeking to understand the human

element in such remote regions. The episode has been named ‘Glimpses of Antarctica’. Rather than starting from zero, PolarPol strongly benefited from HIFMB’s podcast setting and Jan’s experience as a podcaster. By relying on *You, Me & HIFMB* established audience and expertise, the project will have much more impact by reaching larger audiences.

Means for communication used	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Audio and online webpage.	General public, particularly those interested in a critical perspective of science.	To foster a more diverse vision of Antarctica by discussing different national and gender perspectives. In addition, to shed some light on the human aspects of science.	https://hifmb.de/news/podcast/

A9: PolarPol short video (June 2025)

After learning about the *Falling Walls Lab MSCA 2025*, I recorded a two-minute video showcasing PolarPol. In the video, I briefly presented the challenges that the Polar regions face in terms of climate change and human impact. I also explained how PolarPol aimed at understanding the struggles in policymaking, especially the complexities of consensus in decision-making.

Means for communication used	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Video and webpage.	General public.	To increase PolarPol’s visibility by promoting awareness of the Polar regions and how the project tries to explain complex concepts in a simple way.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Hm-q8KGO3jv33i2soThKyZqV7xmXawFm/view?pli=1

A10.1: PolarPol tabletop game (February and March 2025)

Inspired by a training course on Data Visualisation from September 2023 at the University of the Arts, London, I decided to respond to the *Science is Wonderful 2024* call, proposing a decision-making game. The positive feedback led me to design and commission PolarPol, a game where players experience the tension between pursuing their own interests and

collaborating with others in order to achieve a common goal. In collaboration with the Electronic Engineering Department at Royal Holloway, University of London (RHUL), we developed a prototype that emulates the complexities of real-world decision-making. Callum Shingleton-Smith, an electronic engineering technician from RHUL, designed and manufactured the game.

We designed a tabletop game based on the mechanics of an air hockey table, where players must position a puck on specific targets. The game follows four sectors—science, economy, environment, and society—in a sequential process, with time constraints and an increasing level of difficulty. The last challenge is consensus, where all players must cooperate to balance the table and win the game.

A10.2: Organisation of a simulation at the Zukunftstag (April 2025)

The Zukunftstag, or 'Day of the Future' in German, is a yearly event organised by research and higher education institutions in Germany focused on providing students with a showcase of a real day at work. PolarPol prototype was tested during the Zukunftstag with schoolchildren aged 11 to 16.

Our session started with a brief explanation of what is Antarctica, how the regions is governed and how decision-making can be challenging. Then, I invited the group of students to play the game. As my German level was intermediary, the slides were in both languages (English and German), but I also counted with HIFMB support (Leah-Celine Brade), who intermediated my communication with students, guaranteeing a smooth session.

Means for communication used	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Interactive session through a tabletop game made of acrylic and wood (parts printed using a 3D printer and then assembled).	Primary and secondary schools.	Provide a relatable experience of how decision-making in politics takes place, creating awareness about environmental politics within future generations.	https://polarpol.awi.de/work-package-5-communication-and-dissemination/

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES¹

CARRIED OUT ACTIVITIES JUN 2023 – JUL 2025

Publications

Title: *A South American Perspective on Antarctic Geopolitics*

Data: 28.12.2024

Book: Geopolitical Change and the Antarctic Treaty System: Historical Lessons, Current Challenges. Springer Polar Sciences. Springer, Singapore

Link to repository: <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-981-97-9808-7?page=2#toc>

Title: *Antarctic Treaty Secretariat*

Date: 15.08.2025

Book: Elgar Concise Encyclopedia of Polar Law

Link to repository: <https://www.e-elgar.com/shop/gbp/elgar-concise-encyclopedia-of-polar-law-9781035300105.html>

Events

A1: Conferences

Title	Date	Type and Format	MSCA fellow's Role	Target Group(s)	Link (if any)
The Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research 2023 - Humanities and Social Sciences	24.06.2023	Roundtable: South American connections with the Antarctic: historical, political, ideational, cultural and emotional links across the Drake Passage	Speaker	Antarctic Social Science and Humanities scholars	https://scarschas2023.ulsofona.pt/official-program/scholars
Offene Jahrestagung der DVPW-Themengruppe Polar- und Meerespolitik: <i>The Implementation</i>	15.02.2024-16.02.2024	Roundtable: Acquisition of Third-Party Funding for Social Science Polar and Marine Research	Panellist	Polar and Marine social scientists	N/a

<i>of Human and Environmental Risk Measures by European Antarctic Actors (online)</i>		Panel 3: Arctic and Antarctic Governance	Speaker		
Arctic Science Summit Week 2024: <i>Policy briefing best practices (online)</i>	21.03.2024-29.03.2024	Session: EU Polar Cluster: Coordination and networking for Polar cooperation projects	Speaker	European Polar stakeholders	https://www.assw.info/program
European Polar Board Spring Plenary 2024: <i>PolarPol</i>	23.04.2024-24.04.2024	Project introduction	Speaker	European Polar stakeholders	N/a
Arctic Circle Berlin Forum 2024: <i>Constructing the Arctic: 'Bringing Science to Politics</i>	07.05.2024-08.05.2024	Session: Local Actors in Environmental Governance?	Speaker	Polar stakeholders and scholars	https://arctic-circle-www.cdn.prismic.io/arctic-circle-www/ZgR-uct2UUcvBPQv_BerlinForumProgramDraft-BF24-27.03.2024-.pdf
British International Studies Association (BISA): <i>The limits of environmental governance in areas of disputed sovereignty: the implementation of human and environmental risk measures by European Antarctic actors</i>	04.06.2024-07.06.2024	Panel: The Injustices of Law	Speaker	International Law and Politics academics	https://indico.bis.ac.uk/event/347/timetable/?view=standard
The Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research Open Science Conference 2024	19.08.2024-23.08.2024	Antarctic Governance, Science, and Law at the International and Domestic Level	Convenor and discussant	Antarctic scholars	https://scar.org/~documents/route%3A/download/6303
		International Polar Year 2032-33: From Vision to Action	Notetaker		
		Book panel: Colonialism and Antarctica: Attitudes, Logics and Practices	Panellist		

Deutsche Vereinigung für Politikwissenschaft (DVPW): <i>The Antarctic Treaty System and environmental regimes: geopolitical disputes and diplomatic lessons</i>	27.09.2024	Panel: Cold Frontiers in Flux – the Evolving Landscape of Polar Politics: Lessons for Political Science and International Relations	Speaker	Political scientists	https://www.dvpw.de/en/dvpw2024/programme/panels
Arctic Circle Assembly 2024: special sessions	17.10.2024-19.10.2024	Invitation only: Roundtable on Science Diplomacy	Participant	Polar stakeholders and scholars	https://www.arcticcircle.org/assemblies
Arctic Frontiers 2025 Beyond Borders: <i>Might an IPY 2032-33 actually be a problematic idea? The fallacies of geopolitical worldviews in science</i>	27.01.2025-30.01.2025	Science Session on the International Polar Year Part 3	Speaker	Polar stakeholders and scholars	https://arcticfrontiers.com/science/science-themes-2025/

A2: Seminars and Webinars

Title	Date	Type and Format	MSCA fellow's Role	Target Group(s)	Link (if any)
Antártica: desafíos e perspectivas para o século XXI	22.06.2023	Webinar (Instituto de Estudos Estratégicos – Universidade Federal Fluminense)	Speaker	Antarctic scholars, stakeholders and students	https://www.youtube.com/live/OzXOaxtT8mQ?si=7oXcV0Jhn8j--hYp
Compliance versus Implementation in international environmental regimes	06.12.2023	Seminar: Arctic Centre: The Role of States in the Legal Protection of Antarctica	Speaker	Antarctic and international law scholars	https://www.rug.nl/research/arctic-centrum/news/arctic-centre-seminar
PolarPol project	07.02.2024	Webinar: Marine Governance Research Group	Speaker	Marine social scientists and geographers	N/a
Collaborative Governance within the Antarctic Treaty: the role of stakeholders in the Antarctic management	15.05.2024	Webinar: Southern Ocean Summer School 2024	Speaker	Early-career scientists on the Southern Ocean	https://www.europeanpolarboard.org/news-events/news/article/news/southern-ocean-summer-school-2024/

Fourth International Conference on Arctic Research Planning (ICARP IV)	21.10.2024-24.10.2024	Process Planning Retreat - Arctic Science Committee	Notetaker/Facilitator	Arctic and Polar scientists, stakeholders	ICARP IV
PolarPol results	09.04.2025	Seminar: Marine Governance Research Group	Speaker	Marine social scientists and geographers	N/a

A5.2: Workshop

Title	Date	Type and Format	MSCA fellow's Role	Target Group(s)	Link (if any)
Comparison of NPs implementation of human and environmental emergencies measures	07-07-2025-09-07-2025	Workshop: Ant-ICON: The Future of Antarctic and Southern Ocean conservation in a changing climate	Speaker/Notetaker	Antarctic researchers (natural and social sciences), and stakeholders	https://scar.org/s-car-news/programmes/ant-icon-news/workshop-shaping-the-future-2025

Website:

<https://polarpol.awi.de>

Social media:

<https://bsky.app/profile/polarpol.bsky.social/Bluesky>

EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS¹

ACTIVITIES FROM JUL 2025

A11: PolarPol Mark II table-top game (September 2025)

PolarPol is a game that allows students (specifically) and the general public (more broadly) to experience the challenges of decision-making and gain an empirical understanding of the gap between decisions and their implementation. One of the biggest challenges of our time is the rapid spread of fake news: disinformation is increasing polarisation in our societies. The disconnection between expert explanations of global problems—such as climate change—and public understanding feeds disinterest and creates space for misinformation.

By offering a haptic, sensorial experience of decision-making, PolarPol creates a tangible, relatable process that audiences can understand. Based on a decision-making logic applicable across different contexts—from global to local—PolarPol succeeds in communicating complex issues by engaging individuals through direct experience. No one tells them what to think; they all arrive at the same conclusion through play.

After the success of the Zukunftstag in HIFMB, and inspired by the MSCA Falling Walls Venture call, we are currently developing PolarPol Mark II. We aim at continuing using the game for taster sessions in universities and, perhaps, liaise with local councils. We want to take PolarPol to public events as a way to reduce the distance between research and the perception of diplomacy and science by the general public.

What is to be exploited	Technology readiness level (TRL)	Target group and end users	Format	Expected outcome
Tabletop made of acrylic and wood, with sound and vibration sensors.		General public, stakeholders, and natural science academics interested in understanding how policy decisions are made in a sensorial way.	Outreach sessions with schools and, perhaps, councils.	Empowering individuals and restoring trust on science by communicating complex issues through a direct experience.

PLANNED FUTURE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES FROM JUL 2025

A4: HIFMB Policy Brief (Oct 2025)

With the support of the Transfer Office for Marine Biodiversity Change at HIFMB, I will publish the final research results of PolarPol as a Policy Brief, communicating in a simple and effective manner. The training course in Data Visualisation from August and September 2023, in addition to the 'Writing Policy Briefs and Op-Eds: Communicating Research with Policymakers & Community' session, offered by the International Studies Association in April 2025, will be very helpful for this Policy Brief conception.

Moreover, relying both on the consolidated practice of HIFMB in producing policy briefs and on its established audience, the PolarPol Policy Brief will reach larger audiences and inform the main struggles of implementation and policymaking within European National Antarctic Programmes.

Means for communication	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Policy Brief	Polar researchers and stakeholders.	Communicate the results of PolarPol in a simple and effective way.	N/a

A12: PolarPol and researcher website and domain (from Aug 2025)

In July 2025, I have acquired the domains for PolarPol, so a dedicated email address and website is under-construction. The main goal is to gather in a single and professional digital space, all the information about my academic and consultancy trajectories. In addition, I will also share all the outputs from my previous research projects, creating a source of information about the politics of the Polar regions to any interested audience.

Means for communication	Target public(s)	Main goal(s)	Link
Website and email address	Polar researchers and stakeholders, academics from international relations and environmental governance, and the general public.	To create a dedicated space to advertise my credentials as a polar expert and share my research outputs to any interested audience.	

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES FROM JUL 2025

A1: Conference (Aug 2025)

European International Studies Association – 18th Pan-European Conference on International Relations (EISA-PEC)

Title	Date	Type and Format	Role	Target Group(s)
<i>A Look Inside: Domestic Configurations for the Implementation of Human and Environmental Emergency Measures in Antarctica</i>	25.08.2025 – 29.08.2025	Panel: Global Ocean and Polar Justice	Speaker	International Relations and Polar scholars
<i>Living Marine Resource Governance in the Southern Ocean: Converging Perceptions in a Diverging Future</i>		Section: Polar Cultures, International Norms and Geopolitics		
<i>Living Marine Resource Governance in the Southern Ocean: Converging Perceptions in a Diverging Future</i>		Panel: S23 – Global Environmental Politics	Speaker	International Relations and Environmental Governance scholars
		Section: Governing Ocean Challenges		

A3: Publication Strategy Plan (from Jul 2025)

Articles	MSCA outputs	'An Overview of Antarctic Tourism'	Under review
		'Private governance and environmental protection in the frozen south: Antarctic tourism and legitimacy perceptions'	Under review
		'Living Marine Resource governance in the Southern Ocean: converging perceptions in a diverging future'	Under review
		'Cold as ice: the 'estrangement' of international society's primary institutions in Antarctica'	Under review
		'Human and environmental liability in Antarctica: a crossroad'	2026
		'The limits in Antarctic Treaty regime: a comparative analysis'	2026
Monographs	Book	'Environmental Stewardship and Antarctic Governance: Sovereignty, Science and International Society'	<i>Routledge Research in Global Environmental Governance Series</i> Under contract
	Book chapters	'5. Constructing the Arctic III: 'Bringing Science to Politics''	<i>The Worldviews of Ice: Constructions of the Arctic at the Science/Politics Interface</i> Under review

'25. The Future of the "Antarctic Club"'	<i>Handbook on the Politics and Governance of Antarctica: The New Strategic Context - Edward Elgar</i>	2026/27
'2. The objectives of the Environmental Protocol'	<i>Elgar Commentary on the Environmental Protocol</i>	2026/27